

A Novel Method for Generic Geometric Progression

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Abstract

This paper presents a new mathematical theorem on the geometric series which will be very useful for the researchers involving in the research areas such as physical sciences, engineering, medicine, etc.

Keywords: Novel method, mathematical theorem, geometric progression.

Introduction

Geometric series plays a key role in research areas such as physical sciences, engineering, medicine, etc. In this study, a new mathematical theorem is introduced on the geometric series.

Generic Geometric Series

The following theorem is constituted with help of geometric series.

Theorem

$$\sum_{i=k}^{n-1} r^i = \frac{(r^n - r^k)}{(r - 1)} \quad (r \neq 1)$$

where r is any number and $k, n \in \mathbf{Z}$, set of integers.

Proof1

We can the above theorem as follows:

$$r^n = r^n$$

$$r^n = r r^{n-1}$$

$$r^n = (r-1)r^{n-1} + r^{n-1}$$

$$r^n = (r-1)r^{n-1} + (r-1)r^{n-2} + r^{n-2}$$

Similarly, we can continue this mathematical expression as follows

$$r^n = (r-1)r^{n-1} + (r-1)r^{n-2} + \dots + (r-1)r^k + r^k$$

$$\sum_{i=k}^{n-1} r^i = \frac{(r^n - r^k)}{(r-1)}$$

Proof2

We can also prove the theorem $\sum_{i=k}^{q-1} r^i = \frac{(r^q - r^k)}{(r-1)}$ by induction.

Basis

Let $k = 0$.

Then

$$\sum_{i=0}^{q-1} r^i = \frac{(r^q - 1)}{r-1}$$

It is true by actual geometric series formula

Inductive hypothesis

Let us assume that the theorem is true for $k = \pm(n-1)$.

Inductive step

We must prove that the inductive hypothesis is true for $k = \pm n$

As per the theorem, the results are shown as

$$(i) \sum_{i=n}^{q-1} r^i = \frac{(r^q - r^n)}{r-1} \text{ for } k = n$$

$$(ii) \sum_{i=-n}^{q-1} r^i = \frac{(r^q - r^{-n})}{r-1} \text{ for } k = -n$$

Now, the same results using actual geometric series formula are computed as follows:

$$(i) \sum_{i=n}^{q-1} r^i = \sum_{i=0}^{q-1} r^i - \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} r^i = \frac{(r^q - 1)}{(r-1)} - \frac{(r^n - 1)}{r-1} = \frac{(r^q - r^n)}{r-1}$$

$$(ii) \sum_{i=-n}^{q-1} r^i = \sum_{i=-n}^{-1} r^i + \sum_{i=0}^{q-1} r^i = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{r^i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q-1} r^i = \frac{\left(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{r^{n+1}}\right)}{1 - \frac{1}{r}} + \frac{(r^q - 1)}{r - 1}$$

$$i.e. \sum_{i=-n}^{q-1} r^i = \frac{(r^q - r^{-n})}{r - 1}$$

Thus, the inductive hypothesis is true for $k = \pm n$.

Hence, the theorem is proved.

Note that the following mathematical expression is true:

$$\sum_{i=k}^{n-1} ar^i = \frac{a(r^n - r^k)}{(r - 1)} \text{ where } a \text{ is a constant.}$$

Conclusion

In the research study, a new mathematical theorem has been formulated along with detailed proof. This new theorem will be very useful for researchers involving in the research areas such as physical sciences, engineering, medicine, etc.

Reference

- [1] Annamalai, C (2009) A novel computational technique for the geometric progression of powers of two, Journal of Scientific and Mathematical Research, 8, 2pp
(<http://www.jscimath.org/uploads/J200979CA.pdf?CFID=26477055&CFTOKEN=82204266>)